

ADOPTING OPEN BIM TECHNOLOGY FOR THE ANALYSIS AND DETAILING OF CONNECTIONS IN STEEL STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Open BIM is a universal approach to the collaborative design, construction, and maintenance of buildings. It arises from the need to respond to today's increasingly specialised professional situation and the growing need for collaboration to achieve greater efficiency. With this technology, a shared workflow can be established, resulting in significant time and cost reductions, and avoiding many problems arising from the lack of coordination between the design and construction phases. The aim is to integrate new technologies into the development process of a project through a series of tools that facilitate the specialised work of technicians and enable information to be transmitted in a standard digital format. This work presents an Open BIM collaborative workflow to meet the needs of the steel construction industry, specifically in the stages related to modelling and analysing connections between steel structure elements. It allows the use of open standards to import complete structural models into the project and, from them, develop detailed models of the connections for analysis using the finite element method and for generating shop drawings and files for manufacturing the structure. Through the proposal presented, each party contributes by providing different information layers as the project develops. Starting with a basic project model, it is complemented with more detailed information, leading to a more detailed model.

Keywords: Open BIM, Steel detailing, OpenSees, Steel connections, CYPE

1 INTRODUCTION

The management processes of construction projects are improving every year due to the growth of the Architectural Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry and the rapid development of digital technologies. Building Information Modelling (BIM), which has become an indispensable part of this process, has been playing a key role in large-scale construction projects for the last decade upon the advantages it provides in communication and design coordination ^(1,2). BIM is a digital representation of the physical and functional characteristics of a building ⁽¹¹⁾. A BIM model can be thought of as a data repository in which all the construction information for different phases of the project life cycle is integrated. BIM emphasises the sharing and transmission of model information across a project lifecycle ⁽¹²⁾.

The BIM market is projected to grow at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 12.5%, from USD 5.4 billion to USD 10.7 billion from 2020-to 2026 ⁽¹³⁾. BIM's unique selling point is premised upon its inherent capability to create new collaborative work practices ⁽⁸⁾, where project stakeholders (designers, contractors, clients and end-users) have continuous access to up-to-date digital building data via a common data environment (CDE).

BIM workflows have been applied to the most diverse cases, from simple conventional projects to more advanced uses of the information contained in the models. Workflows that connect different project phases, such as architectural modelling and structural design, are becoming increasingly common ⁽⁹⁾. Cost estimation studies and energy calculations using BIM technology are also

becoming popular ⁽¹⁰⁾ In the case of the steel structures industry, BIM is especially useful, since the degree of industrialisation of this type of structure is higher than that usually found in other areas of the AEC sector. Even some cloud-based workflows have been presented and used in the design of steel structures before ^(4,5), and the conclusions of these studies show that the use of BIM technology in the structural engineering sector only brings benefits to everyone involved, both in the design, manufacturing and assembly phases. CYPE Connect, for example, is a tool created specifically for modelling and analysing connections in steel structures using the finite element method (FEM) ⁽⁵⁾. Using the OpenSees analyses engine ⁽⁷⁾ a simulation can be carried out and the results automatically compared with different requirements established by different industry standards.

The aim of this paper is to present a summary of some of the technologies used in the steel structure construction industry and to propose a method, combining a series of BIM applications, which makes it possible to use the same model of a steel connection for analysing, designing, documenting, quantifying, and manufacturing it.

2 OPEN BIM

Data interoperability between the software applications employed by several specialists involved in construction processes has been one of the challenges in the industry ⁽³⁾. As a neutral data format, Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) is widely used to facilitate the exchange of information between the specialists involved and the digital tools they use, enabling them to reuse models without having to create them from scratch ⁽⁶⁾. Instead of working off proprietary native files such as Autodesk Revit (.rvt) files or GraphiSoft ArchiCAD (.PLA) files, in a spirit of interoperability, the prototype web platform uses the vendor-neutral IFC (.ifc) files as input. This widens the potential beneficiary base, as the solution is not tied to one vendor. IFC files come in many versions in the form of Model View Definitions (MVDs).

3 PROPOSED WORKFLOW

While in the construction industry, the manufacturing of steel structures is one of the most developed and automated sectors, there are still gaps in the industrialisation process. Although there are advanced BIM modelling tools that offer some interesting results for structural steel projects, until now no workflow has had a process that guarantees the connection of all the parties involved in the project, from its initial conception, through modelling and analysis (especially when it comes to connections), to its fabrication. Given this situation and the context of Open BIM technology presented above, this article proposes a workflow that can meet this need.

3.1 Overview of the workflow

The workflow proposed in this paper is divided into four main parts, which are described by the letters a, b, c and d in the flowchart in Fig. 1.

The input of data (Figure 1a) can be done in different ways and different formats can be used. On the one hand, the geometry of the structure can be entered using traditional CAD formats, such as .dwg or .dxf, and then the structural analysis of the model can be carried out in phase b using CYPE 3D. This process is indicated by the red line in the flowchart in Figure 1.

In addition to entering files in CAD format, the geometry of the structure can also be entered in .ifc format, in which case the IFC file must be created using the entities *IFCStructuralPointConnection*, for the definition of nodes and their external fixity conditions, and *IFCStructuralCurveMember* for bars with their end fixity conditions and their descriptions. In phase b, when used alongside the

geometry imported from the formats described in phase a, it is also possible to model a steel structure from scratch using CYPE 3D's native modelling system.

Another way to enter data is to use BIM models created in modelling software, such as Autodesk Revit, Archicad, Tekla or other BIM modelling software (represented by the blue lines in the flowchart in figure 1). In this case, the BIM model must contain structural steel elements and be exported to IFC format from the modelling software. In this case, the IFC file will have to be added to a CDE, where other Open BIM tools will be integrated into the workflow. The CDE proposed in this case is BIMserver.center, which supports workflows using IFC files and other formats based on open standards. In order to upload the IFC file to the BIMserver.center platform, the "IFC Uploader" support tool, which can be downloaded free of charge from the platform itself, should be used. In this workflow, the structural analysis phase will not exist, and it is understood that the structural model has already been analysed and designed beforehand and, therefore, phase b no longer exists.

* IFC file must be created using the entities *IFCStructuralPointConnection* and *IFCStructuralCurveMember*

Fig. 1. Workflow proposed in this article.

In the case of phase b, when it is considered, the different boundary conditions of the structure will be defined; buckling conditions of the bars; considerations for fixing the nodes and the different loads, including accidental loads, self-weight, snow, wind, and seismic actions. The combinations and design load cases will also be defined, as well as the characteristics of the materials to be used. CYPE 3D also offers the option of selecting a structural design code, and its library includes codes from different countries, which will be used as a reference for designing the steel element sections, as well as checking them according to the code selected. The result of phase b will be a BIM model of the structure that contains the final geometry of the structure, although it will not yet include the detailed definition of the connections. This model can be exported in IFC for use in phase c of the proposed workflow.

In phase c, "Modelling and analysing the connections", the two variations of this workflow (red and blue) converge. From this point onwards, the process is similar in both cases. Depending on the

process followed (red or blue), some types of data will be available for the analysis of connections, while others will not. This subject is dealt with in more detail in point 4.1.

The program used in phase 3 is CYPE Connect, which is used for modelling, analysing, checking standards, and documenting connections in steel structures. The structure's IFC files synchronised with CDE (BIMserver.center) can be read by CYPE Connect and, using the information contained in the structure's BIM model, each connection can be modelled, analysed, and then documented. More details about the modelling process of the connections as well as their analysis using the finite element method (FEM) with the OpenSees framework are described in section 0.

The combination of the structure's geometry defined in phase b (or imported directly from phase a) with the connections modelled in phase c (CYPE Connect) can be used to create a detailed model of the structure that contains all the data needed for the automated fabrication of the structure using the StruBIM Steel program. This combination is made by consolidating the federated model (in this case containing the bars of the structure in one IFC and the connections in another) into a single file, which can then be exported in different formats adapted to the machines used to manufacture structures. More details on this process are covered in section 4.5.3.

4 MODELING CONNECTIONS AND ANALYSING THEM THROUGH THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

Phase c begins when the IFC containing the structure's geometry is imported into CYPE Connect. At this point, the program will recognise all the nodes in the structure and list them so that their respective connections can be modelled and subsequently analysed. Each connection can be modelled using the "Connection Editor", where a series of successive operations can be carried out with the aim of "treating the node" and transforming it into a connection that can actually be manufactured.

4.1 Modelling connections

In CYPE Connect's "Connection editor", until version 2024.f of the program, there were operations for creating reference planes; adding complementary sections; adding plates, welds, and bolts; modifying and adjusting steel sections such as trimming, openings, extensions, rounding corners; entering anchoring elements and stiffeners, among others.

Fig. 2. Connection editor based on a list of operations.

The modelling process is relatively simple. By simply selecting one of the operations from the main toolbar (Fig. 2a), it be added to the list of operations in the left-hand column (Fig. 2b). In the central area of the screen, the characteristics of the selected operation that need to be filled in will appear (Fig. 2c). On the right-hand side, as operations are added and customised, the connection model is formed (Fig. 2d). Occasionally, during the modelling, certain inconsistencies may occur, such as missing, disconnected, or repeated elements, or clashing geometries. The program issues warnings about these incidents in the bar at the bottom of the screen (Fig. 2e).

4.2 Types of connections

CYPE Connect's modelling operations allow different types of connections to be modelled (Fig. 3). Among the different combinations, it is possible to create connections between two or more steel elements, between two or more timber elements or a combination of both materials. These combinations can also include modelling operations to define anchoring elements for the connection to other reinforced concrete structural elements, such as the foundation plates or lateral anchors in concrete beams or walls.

Fig. 3. a) Connections between two or more steel elements; b) Connections between two or more timber elements; c) Combination between elements of both materials; d) Anchors.

4.3 Entering loads and combinations

Once the connection has been modelled, the next step is to continue to the structural analysis of the connection. The first data that needs to be considered in the analysis will be the load cases. These load cases can be generated from the BIM model (only when phase b of the workflow proposed in section 2 has been considered) or configured manually by the user. The following parameters are defined for each load case: number of load steps; tolerance allowed to consider that convergence has been achieved; maximum number of iterations in each load step and maximum number of retries.

The next step is to define the loads acting on each of the members that reach the node. These loads can be entered manually, by pasting data from Microsoft Excel tables, or the loads can be imported automatically from the BIM model (when CYPE 3D has been used to generate the structure's IFC). In addition to the loads, the position of the force application point can be defined for each section. This distance will also be read in the BIM model, as long as the structure has been analysed considering the finite dimension of the nodes. An additional option available to users is to select the members from which the rotational stiffness of the connection could be analysed. To calculate the "Rotational stiffness" users will need a list of loads, the lengths of the elastic member in the structural model (used to establish the limit stiffness of rigid or fixed connections).

4.4 OpenSees software framework

At this point in the workflow, the connections modelled using the set of operations will be analysed

using OpenSees, which will be run as an integrated part of CYPE Connect, and the program will then report the results of the analysis and compare them with the limits established by the previously selected standard, pre-configured by the user. Considering this, CYPE Connect is a tool that allows users to generate models of steel structure connections based on finite elements including their analysis and verification according to standard requirements, with minimal or no user intervention, using the finite element program, OpenSees, as an analysis engine. OpenSees is a software framework for developing applications to simulate the performance of structural and geotechnical systems subjected to earthquakes ⁽⁷⁾. Previously published works by Gómez et al ⁽⁵⁾ describe the details of how the finite element analysis is carried out.

4.5 Parameters included in the structural analysis.

The results of the structural analysis of the connection can be expressed in different ways, some of which are detailed in the following sections:

4.5.1 Results related to stress/strain analysis.

Through the results of the maximum demand capacity ratio (Fig. 4a), the elements that make up the connection are shown in a certain colour according to their percentage of use. Elements indicated in red have exceeded the safety limit and need to be reconsidered. For sections and plates, deformation is checked by setting a plastic deformation limit of 5%. For welds, the strength of the fillet weld is checked. For bolts, the edge and bolt distance, tensile strength, shear strength and bearing strength are checked, as well as the interaction between shear and tension. For prestressed bolts, slip resistance is also tested.

Fig. 4. Different results from finite element analysis. a) Maximum demand capacity ratio. b) Von Mises stress. c) Equivalent Von Mises deformation. d) Displacements.

The results for the Von Mises Stress can also be found, both in connection check reports and graphically through a three-dimensional representation of the stress distributions next to their discretisation (Fig. 4b). In the same way, the results for the Equivalent Von Mises deformation (Fig. 4c) and the displacements (Fig. 4d) can also be obtained.

4.5.2 Linear buckling analysis

Another analysis that can be carried out is the local buckling of each bar in each connection, which occurs due to compression forces and mostly depends on the stiffness of the component and the distribution of the applied loads. The buckling analysis helps to detect unstable connection design configurations under the load of a particular load case. There are several ways to evaluate the buckling phenomenon using finite elements. The one implemented in the connection analysis of

CYPE Connect is the "Linear buckling analysis" which allows users to obtain the critical load factors of the different local buckling modes of the connection for a given load case. Once the analysis is completed, the critical load factors are obtained for each of the buckling modes as well as their deformed shape. The smaller the first critical load factor, the closer the users are to an unstable connection configuration.

Fig. 5. Example of a connection for which linear buckling analysis has been conducted. This case shows three buckling modes (a, b, and c) for one of the analysed load combinations.

4.5.3 Rotational stiffness

The rotational stiffness of a bar reaching the node can also be analysed. In this case, CYPE Connect allows users to obtain the resistant moment, the initial stiffness, the secant stiffness, and the classification of the connection (rigid, semi-rigid or pinned) of the steel sections. As part of the results, some graphs (Fig. 6b) show the curves for "Moment - Rotation", "Acting moment of the selected load case", "Resistant moment", "Ultimate stiffness for rigid connections (Sj,1)" and "Ultimate stiffness for pinned connections (Sj,2)". To classify the connection as rigid, semi-rigid or pinned, the limit stiffnesses of rigid and pinned connections must first be established. Depending on the selected steel codes, the initial stiffness or the secant stiffness will be compared with these limits.

Fig. 6. Example of a connection where the rotational stiffness of the beam reaching the column has been determined. In this case the connection was classified as semi-rigid. a) BIM model of the connection. b) "Moment-Rotation" graph.

4.6 Iterative analysis considering the rotational stiffness of the connections in the global analysis of the structure

An interesting analysis that can be carried out when combining CYPE 3D and CYPE Connect in the same workflow is the possibility of optimising connection analyses through an iterative analysis. In this case, the data obtained from the results of the global analysis of the structure in CYPE 3D (forces in the nodes and size of the steel cross-sections), where the stiffnesses of the nodes were initially estimated using simplified values (usually from the literature), are exported to CYPE Connect to determine the stiffness of these same nodes more precisely. These stiffnesses analysed by FEM in CYPE Connect can in turn be returned to CYPE 3D for a more accurate analysis of the distribution of forces in the structure, in this case with more approximate rotational stiffness values. In an iterative process, the results obtained in CYPE 3D can be exported back to CYPE Connect, where another iteration can be carried out and the results can be further optimised. The process can be repeated as many times as deemed appropriate to determine the accuracy of the results.

This process can contain a large number of analysed and updated connections. Therefore, in a reasonably large structure, it would be practically impossible to carry out this process manually. This is where the Open BIM workflow and the use of a CDE capable of integrating this type of tool, such as BIMserver.center, come into their own. In the case of the link between CYPE 3D and CYPE Connect, data travels from one program to another, regardless of direction, through the cloud via "contributions" that are exported and received in both programs. This system even allows different professionals to work on this process, one of whom could be working on the global analysis of the structure and the other on the local analysis of the connections, with both communicating through CDE.

5 RESULTS THAT CAN BE OBTAINED BEYOND ANALYSIS

5.1 Manufacturing models

Both the link model and the complete structure model can be exported to different formats, including DSTV and STEP formats. The export options in STEP format can be carried out by including both the complete structure (Structure) and the individual parts (Parts). The STEP format (ISO 10303) allows data to be exchanged between design and manufacturing systems (CAD, CAM, CAE). The DSTV file format is an industry standard defined by the German steel construction association Deutsche Stahlbau-Verband.

5.2 Sheets in DWG, DXF or PDF format

All the details of the modelled connections can be represented on paper with the intention of creating shop drawings. Sheets generated in StruBIM Steel (or directly through CYPE Connect when the connection is modelled separately) via the options contained in the "Structural steel detailing drawings" module can be exported in DWG, DXF or PDF format.

5.3 Export detailing of the steel structure in IFC EM.11 (Exchange Model 11)

Another option for exporting the detailed structural model is to export it in IFC format. This option allows the model to be integrated into the BIM project, along with the other models that make up the building in other modelling tools. Through this integration, different uses can be given to this model (graphic representation, quantification of materials, clash detection analysis, compatibility with other disciplines, etc.). In this specific case, the exported file will be in IFC EM.11. EM.11 is an MVD (Model View Definition) specification of the IFC format containing information for automated steel fabrication. StruBIM Steel exports using this format for sections, plates, welds, bolts, and screws.

Fig. 7. a) Finished structural model for manufacturing that includes analysed connections. b) Structural model exported in IFC and visualized in free visualization software (BIM Vision).

5.4 Project reports and quantities reports

Different types of structure-related reports can be generated and exported in different formats. Among the main reports are regulatory check reports and reports containing lists of materials. The options available for generating complete quantities reports; reports for a selection of assemblies or for a for a selection of parts.

5.5 Augmented reality and virtual reality models

The developed model, when created using two or more Open BIM tools synchronised through the CDE (BIMserver.center), can automatically be represented in virtual reality (VR) or augmented reality (AR) through the BIMserver.center Augmented Reality (compatible with the Windows mixed reality portal) and BIMserver.center Mobile (compatible with Android and iOS) tools respectively. Through these models, the geometry and information of the structure can be visualised and consulted in the field in an immersive way, including the possibility of representing the model at full scale.

Fig. 8. Augmented reality model of a structure analyzed and detailed using the proposed workflow.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a workflow that optimises the process of modelling, analysing, and checking steel structures, especially those that contain complex connections between their elements, with the aim of connecting all phases of the project, from its initial conception to its fabrication. Based on this, some conclusions are presented below.

- The fact that the same model used to fabricate the structure is used for structural analysis (using OpenSees) brings greater precision, agility, and safety to the project, since this process eliminates any duplicates, and no elements need to be remodelled or manually inserted twice.
- The use of a workflow based on the IFC standard (Open BIM) makes the process more flexible and allows different professionals, including professionals from other areas related

to structural engineering, to work in an integrated and simultaneous way through the CDE (BIMserver.center). The use of IFC makes it possible to use software from different developers throughout the process.

- The interoperability between the global structural analysis program (CYPE 3D) and the structural analysis program for connections (CYPE Connect) increases the agility, precision and safety of the structural analysis as a whole, since different data such as loads, load cases, node geometry and rotational stiffnesses can be sent from one program to the other (and vice versa) automatically and without the need for manual data entry.

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